

Attitude Towards Sex Education Among Secondary School Students in Namchi District of Sikkim

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Abstract

This study explores the attitudes of secondary school students in Namchi district, South Sikkim, towards sex education. The research aims to understand the differences in attitudes based on gender and locale. A quantitative research methodology was employed, utilizing a standardized questionnaire developed by Usha Mishra (2008) to gather data from 160 students from Class IX and X. The findings reveal that the majority of students hold positive attitudes towards sex education. There is no significant difference between boys and girls, indicating that both genders are equally receptive. However, urban students, have a more positive attitude as compared to rural students. This suggests that geographic location influences attitudes, with urban areas providing better exposure and resources. To address these disparities, tailored educational programs should be implemented, focusing on enhancing sex education in rural areas to ensure all students benefit equally.

Keywords: Sex Education, Attitude, Urban Area, Rural Area, Secondary School Students.

Introduction

Sex education plays a significant role in a child's development, providing them with the knowledge to understand themselves and their environment. It empowers young people to recognize potential risks and protect themselves, raising awareness about the dangers of sexual exploitation (Lavanya et al.,2011). It encompasses a wide range of topics like sexual anatomy, behavior, health, relationships, STIs, birth control, and reproductive rights. It also addresses decision-making, communication, and values. The primary objectives is to guide individuals in developing responsible attitudes and behaviors towards sexuality (Fentahun et al., 2012; Guha,2013). Western civilization highlights the importance of complementing family teachings with school-based sex education. This education promotes sexual health by providing a positive, fact-based view of sexuality, encouraging wise and responsible decisions, and offering a balanced perspective on sexual issues (Qasim, 2013). The significance of sex education for children is an issue that is widely discussed around the world and has to be publicly acknowledged. There has been disagreement over this issue; some people support it and others do not. However, many young people nowadays are victims of sexually transmitted diseases and misinformation (Sunder,2018).

Sex education in schools is vital for informing students about gender, sexual health, and preventing risky behaviors like early sexual activity. It promotes healthy relationships, addresses gender and identity issues, and corrects myths about sexuality. In India, with rising risks among youth – such as early pregnancy, STIs, and violence – sex education is especially crucial. Parents and educators must acknowledge its importance amidst changing sexual norms (Ismail et al., 2015; Sule, 2015; Saimons & Saba, 2019; Alekhya et al., 2023). In the context of India, the absence of proper sex education leads to a state of substantial perplexity among adolescents, amplifying the enigmatic nature of sexual taboos in their perception (Lavanya et al.,2011; Vashistha & Rajshree,2012). Sexuality education serves to shield children from negative experiences by safeguarding them against sexual harassment and inappropriate

contact. It also instructs them on how to effectively respond if they face such situations (Zhang & Yu,2023).

Global experiences demonstrated that sexuality education curricula are among the most effective strategies for implementing reproductive health policies. Many parents hesitate to discuss topics like bodily development and sex with their children due to challenges in finding the right language, discomfort, and concerns about the accuracy of information. Nevertheless, most parents acknowledge the critical role they play in their children's sexuality education (Yuodeshko,2023).Sex education must be implemented in the classroom, beginning in the primary grades and introducing age-appropriate subjects as students advance to the high school level (Qasim, 2013; Kumar et al., 2017).

For a teenager to manage the changes occurring during the adolescent phase, they should be familiar with sex education (Siva et al.,2021). Sex education can aid in a child's development into a well-adjusted adult with a secure sense of their sexual identity and capacity (Mutha et al.,2014). Despite the numerous advantages of sex education, its integration into school curricula is still difficult because of social enmity, cultural restrictions, and the impact of obsolete public attitudes. The lack of involvement of parents and teachers in sexuality education is mostly due to this lack of support (Banerjee & Rao,2022). Promoting sexual literacy and health among adolescents necessitates active participation from both parents and educators. Parents are primarily expected to impart social, cultural, and religious values related to intimate and sexual relationships, while health and education professionals should focus on delivering accurate information about sexuality and fostering relevant social skills (Shtarkshall et al.,2007).

In India, children typically start secondary school at age thirteen, marking the beginning of adolescence. This period is characterized by increased sexual curiosity and behavior, making adolescents particularly vulnerable to HIV infection. About half of all HIV infections occur in individuals aged 15 to 24. If current trends persist, the number of young people infected with HIV/AIDS is expected to rise. In India, 15% of HIV/AIDS patients are children under 15. Awareness about sexuality among Indian adolescents is extremely low, with parents and teachers rarely providing advice or information (Saimons & Saba,2019). Ultimately, sex education empowers young individuals to make informed and responsible choices concerning their sexual health and well-being (Adiaha et al.,2018).

Objectives:

- To find out the level of attitude of secondary school students towards sex education.
- To study and compare the attitude of secondary school students towards sex education with reference to gender (boys & girls).
- To study and compare the attitude of secondary school students towards sex education with reference to locale (urban & rural).

Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in relation to their attitude towards sex education.

H₀2: There is no significant difference between urban and rural secondary school students in relation to their attitude towards sex education.

H₀3: There is no significant difference between Urban boys and urban girls, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education.

H₀4: There is no significant difference between Rural boys and Rural girls, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education.

H₀5: There is no significant difference between Urban boys and Rural boys, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education.

H₀6: There is no significant difference between Urban girls and Rural girls, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education.

Methodology:

This study aimed to assess the attitudes towards sex education among secondary school students in Namchi district, using a quantitative research approach with a standardized questionnaire. The study focused on Class IX and X students, aged 13-16, from government schools in Namchi district. A

descriptive survey research design was employed, utilizing stratified random sampling to ensure balanced representation, a total of 160 students (80 boys and 80 girls) were selected from eight schools (four urban and four rural). The Attitude towards Sex Education Scale developed by Usha Mishra (2008) was used to gather data on students' knowledge, perceptions, and comfort levels regarding sex education.

Results

Finding of objective one:

The level of attitude of secondary school students towards sex education.

Data presented in Table 1 indicates that a significant proportion of secondary school students have a positive attitude towards sex education. Specifically, 0.62% and 2.49% of students demonstrate a very high attitude, scoring between 120-129 and above, while 18.74% students fall within the 110-119 range, and 49.99% student scored between 107-109, indicating a high attitude towards sex education. Additionally, 26.87% of students scored between 90-99, indicating a moderate positive attitude, and 1.24% students scored between 80-89, demonstrating a moderate attitude towards sex education. The findings suggest that secondary school students, have a positive and receptive attitude towards sex education.

Table -1 Frequency scores on Attitude towards Sex Education

Score Range	Stanine Grade	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation
Above 129	9	1	0.62%	Very High Attitude towards Sex Education
120-129		4	2.49%	
110-119	8	30	18.74%	High Attitude towards Sex Education
100-109	7	80	49.99%	
90-99	6	43	26.87%	Moderate Attitude towards Sex Education
80-89	5	2	1.24%	

Finding of Objective Two:

To study and compare the attitude of secondary school students towards sex education with reference to gender (boys & girls).

The data presented in table 2 indicates that in secondary schools, both boys and girls student displays a positive attitudes towards sex education. Specifically, 0.62% boys scored above 129 and 0.62% of boys and 1.87% of girls student scores between 120-129, indicating very high attitude towards sex education. Moreover, 8.12% of boys and 10.62% of girls student scored between 110-119, and a significant percentage of 26.87% of boys and 23.12% of girls students scored between 100-109, indicating a high attitude towards sex education. Furthermore, 13.12% of boys and 13.75 of girls student showed score between 90-99, and a small percentage of 0.62% of boys and 0.62% of girls student scored between 80-89, reflecting a moderate attitude towards sex education. These findings collectively suggest that student in secondary schools exhibit positive and high attitudes towards sex education.

Table- 2 Interpretation of Values of Attitude Towards Sex Education Among Boys and Girls Secondary School Student

Score Range	Frequency		Percentage		Interpretation
	Boys	Girls	Boys	Girls	
Above 129	1		0.62%		Very High Attitude towards Sex Education
120-129	1	3	0.62%	1.87%	
110-119	13	17	8.12%	10.62%	

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100-109	43	37	26.87%	23.12%	High Attitude towards Sex Education
90-99	21	22	13.12%	13.75%	Moderate Attitude towards Sex Education
80-89	1	1	0.62%	0.62%	

Finding of Objective Three:

To study and compare the attitude of secondary school students towards sex education with reference to locale (urban & rural).

The data presented in Table 3 reveals that 1.87% of Urban girls student have very high attitude towards sex education scored between 120-129. Additionally, 5.62 % of urban girls and 5% of rural girls scored between 110-119, and a significant percentage of 11.87% of urban girls and 11.25% of rural girls scored between 100-109, indicating a high attitude towards sex education. Furthermore, 5% of urban girls, 8.75% of rural girls displayed score between 90-99 and a small percentage 0.62% of rural girl scored between 80-89, reflecting a moderate attitude towards sex education.

Table-3 Frequency scores of Urban girls and Rural girls student on Attitude towards Sex Education

Score Range	Stanine Grade	Frequency		Percentage		Interpretation
		Urban girls	Rural girls	Urban girls	Rural girls	
Above 129	9					Very High Attitude towards Sex Education
120-129		3		1.87%		
110-119	8	9	8	5.62%	5%	High Attitude towards Sex Education
100-109	7	19	18	11.87%	11.25%	
90-99	6	8	14	5%	8.75%	Moderate Attitude towards Sex Education
80-89	5	1		0.62%		

The data presented in Table 4 indicates that 0.62% of urban boys student exhibit a very high attitude towards sex education with scores above 129, and 0.62% of urban boys scored between 120-129. Moving on to the 110-119 range, 5.62% of urban boys and 2.50% of rural boys fall into this category. A notable proportion of both urban boys (11.25%) and rural boys (15.62%) scored between 100-109, indicating a high attitude towards sex education. Furthermore, 6.87% of urban boys, 6.25% of rural boys, and a small percentage of rural boys (0.62%) demonstrated a moderate attitude with scores between 80-89 in relation to sex education. Overall, these findings highlight variations in attitudes towards sex education between urban and rural boys, with both groups generally displaying positive and open attitudes towards this topic.

Table - 4 Frequency scores of Urban boys and Rural boys student on Attitude towards Sex Education

Score Range	Stanine Grade	Frequency		Percentage		Interpretation
		Urban boys	Rural boys	Urban boys	Rural boys	
Above 129	9	1		0.62%		Very High Attitude towards Sex Education

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120-129	1			0.62%			
110-119	8	9	4	5.62%	2.50%	High Attitude towards Sex Education	
100-109	7	18	25	11.25%	15.62%		
90-99	6	11	10	6.87%	6.25%	Moderate Attitude towards Sex Education	
80-89	5		1		0.62%		

Difference between male and female secondary school students in relation to their attitude towards sex education

It is revealed from Table 5 that the mean score and standard deviation on attitude towards sex education for boys student were (M=104.23, S.D. = 7.49) and for girls student, it was (M=105, S.D. =7.85) respectively. Further when both the mean values were subjected to the testing of their significance of difference, the finding shows that there is no significant difference between boys and girls student with (t (158) =0.62, p= 0.53(p >.05). It means boys and girls student do not differ significantly in their attitude towards sex education. Since the calculated 't' value is lower than the criterion 't' value. Hence the stated null hypotheses "There is no significant difference between male and female secondary school students in relation to their attitude towards sex education" is failed to be rejected.

Table - 5
Results of t-test Examining the Difference between Boys and Girls
Secondary School Students with Regards to their Attitude Towards Sex Education

Variable	Boys (80)		Girls (80)		t (158)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Attitude towards sex education	104.23	7.49	105	7.85	0.62	0.26

Difference between urban and rural secondary school students in relation to their attitude towards sex education

It is revealed from table 6 that the mean score and standard deviation on attitude towards sex education for urban student were (M= 105.88, S.D. =8.63) and for rural student, it was M= 103.35, S.D. = 6.36) respectively. Further when both the mean values were subjected to the testing of their significance of difference, the finding shows that there is a significant difference between urban and rural students with t (158) =2.10, p= 0.03(p<.05). It means urban and rural students do differ significantly in their attitude towards sex education. Since the calculated 't' value is greater than the criterion 't' value, it can be concluded that there is a significant difference between the attitude of urban and rural students towards sex education at the secondary school level. Hence the stated null hypothesis "There is no significant difference between urban and rural secondary school students in relation to their attitude towards sex education" is rejected.

Table- 6
Results of T-Test Examining the Difference Between Urban and
Rural Secondary School Students with Regards to their Attitude Towards Sex Education

Variable	Urban(80)		Rural (80)		t (158)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Attitude towards sex education	105.88	8.6	103.35	6.3	2.10	0.03

Difference between Urban boys and urban girls, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education.

The table 7 describes that the mean score and standard deviation on attitude towards sex education for urban boys students were (M= 105.65, S.D. =8.60) and for urban girls student, it was (M=106.12, S.D. =8.66) respectively. Further when both the mean values were subjected to the testing of their significance of difference, the finding shows that there is no significant difference between urban boys and urban girls student with $t(158) = 0.24, p = 0.80 (p > .05)$. It means urban boys and urban girls student do not differ significantly in their attitude towards sex education. Since the calculated 't' value is lower than the criterion 't' value. Hence the stated null hypotheses "There is no significant difference between Urban boys and urban girls, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education" is failed to be rejected.

Table-7
Results of t-test examining the difference between Urban Boys and Urban Girls Secondary School Students with regards to their Attitude towards Sex Education

Variable	Urban boys(40)		Urban girls (40)		t (158)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Attitude towards sex education	105.65	8.60	106.12	8.66	0.24	0.80

Difference between Rural boys and Rural girls, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education.

It is revealed from table 8 that the mean score and standard deviation on attitude towards sex education for rural boys student were (M= 102.82, S.D. =5.86) and for rural girls student, it was (M=103.87, S.D. =6.78) respectively. Further when both the mean values were subjected to the testing of their significance of difference, the finding shows that there is no significant difference between rural boys and rural girls student with $t(158) = 0.73, p = 0.46 (p > .05)$. It means rural boys and rural girls student do not differ significantly in their attitude towards sex education. Since the calculated 't' value is lower than the criterion 't' value. Hence the stated null hypotheses "There is no significant difference between Rural boys and Rural girls, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education" is failed to be rejected.

Table - 8
Results of t-test examining the difference between Rural Boys and Rural Girls Secondary School Students with regards to their attitude towards Sex education

Variable	Rural boys (40)		Rural girls (40)		t (158)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Attitude towards sex education	102.82	5.86	103.87	6.87	0.73	0.46

Difference between Urban boys and Rural boys, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education

It is revealed from table 9 that the mean score and standard deviation on attitude towards sex education for urban boys student were (M= 105.65, S.D. =8.60) and for rural boys student, it was (M= 102.82, S.D. =5.86) respectively. Further when both the mean values were subjected to the testing of their significance of difference, the finding shows that there is no significant difference between urban boys and rural boys student with $t(158) = 1.69, p = 0.09 (p > .05)$. It means urban boys and rural boys student do not differ significantly in their attitude towards sex education. Since the calculated 't' value is lower than the criterion 't' value. Hence the stated null hypotheses "There is no significant difference between Urban boys and Rural boys, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education" is failed to be rejected.

Table- 9

**Results of t-Test Examining the Difference Between Urban Boys and Rural Boys
Secondary School Students with Regards to their Attitude Towards Sex Education**

Variable	Urban boys (40)		Rural boys (40)		t (158)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Attitude towards sex education	105.65	8.60	102.82	5.86	1.69	0.09

Difference between Urban girls and Rural girls, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education

The table 10 shows that the mean score and standard deviation on attitude towards sex education for urban girls student were (M= 106.12, S.D. =8.66) and for rural girls student, it was (M=103.87, S.D. =6.78) respectively. Further when both the mean values were subjected to the testing of their significance of difference, the finding shows that there is no significant difference between urban and rural student with $t(158) = 2.10, p = 0.03 (p > .05)$. It means urban girls and rural girls student do not differ significantly in their attitude towards sex education. Since the calculated 't' value is lower than the criterion 't' value. Hence the stated null hypotheses "There is no significant difference between Urban girls and Rural girls, secondary school students, in relation to their attitude towards sex education" is failed to be rejected.

Table- 10

**Results of t-test examining the difference between Urban girls and Rural girls
Secondary School Students with regards to their Attitude towards Sex Education**

Variable	Urban girls (40)		Rural girls (40)		t (158)	p
	M	SD	M	SD		
Attitude towards sex education	106.12	8.66	103.87	6.87	1.27	0.20

Discussion

The current research findings shows that both boys and girls have positive attitude towards sex education which aligns with the study done by Adiaha et al., (2018), which indicate that adolescents, both male and female, exhibit a notably positive attitude towards sexuality education. The findings of this study indicate that majority of the respondents had positive attitude towards sex education, this finding is in accordance with Ademuyiwa et al.,(2023) findings that most secondary school students in south-western Nigeria have a good understanding of sex education. The current study, found no significant difference between boys' and girls' attitudes, unlike a study by Raju and Uprety (2021) on attitudes towards sex education among secondary school students and teachers in East Sikkim reported that male students had a more positive attitude towards sex education compared to female students. Regarding the attitude of secondary school students towards sex education with reference to gender it shows that, both boys and girls have shown similar attitudes towards sex education. A similar study was conducted by Kumar et al., (2017) and found that boys were more likely to favor sex education compared to girls. This shift suggests a change in perceptions over time, indicating increased acceptance and understanding of the importance of sex education among both genders. There is a significant difference between urban and rural secondary students. Supporting the present studies, Saimons & Saba (2019) have also found significant difference. Both studies found that urban boys are more aware of sex education as compare to their counterparts, rural boys. But both the studies found no significant difference in sex education between rural boys and rural girls. The present study found that both urban and rural girls don't have significant difference in the attitude towards sex education. However, the findings of Lalnunfeli & Malsawmi (2018) opposes the current study indicating that rural females have a more positive attitude towards sex education than rural males. Urban female students also exhibit a higher attitude towards sex education compared to their urban male counterparts.

Conclusion

Recognizing sex as a natural aspect of life, it's crucial to discuss it maturely without endorsing specific behaviors. This understanding underscores the importance of integrating sex education into people's lives, particularly for young individuals in high schools. Sex education encompasses various aspects like sexual development, emotions, body image, gender roles, and understanding how we evolve physically and emotionally over time.

Furthermore, sex education promotes a positive view of sexuality and fosters sexual safety awareness. It equips youth with knowledge and skills to navigate life changes like puberty, menopause, and aging, fostering self-esteem and preparedness for adolescence. This education also aids in dispelling fears or misconceptions, such as girls feeling anxious about their first menstruation when they are informed about it beforehand. Studies have shown that young individuals who receive sex education are more likely to practice safer sex and exhibit mature, responsible behavior.

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